

ZIGMA MEDICARE INDIA (OPC) PRIVATE LIMITED

No.26 A, Balaji Nagar, East Zone, Coimbatore – 641048

In Association with .,

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CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

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Interactive Streamlit Application For Airbnb Analytics And Trends.

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ABSTRACT :

The goal of this project is to provide a comprehensive analysis of Airbnb listings, focusing on key aspects such as location, pricing, availability, and guest reviews. By utilizing real-world datasets, this study explores patterns, trends, and insights that can assist hosts, potential investors, and stakeholders in making data-driven decisions.

Keywords: Airbnb Analytics, Streamlit Dashboard, Short-term Rental Trends, Data Visualization, Pricing Analysis, Customer Insights, Geographic Distribution, Machine Learning in Hospitality, Travel and Tourism Data, Interactive Data Exploration, Seasonal Demand Analysis, Real Estate Market Insights

1. INTRODUCTION :

The use of Streamlit enhances the accessibility of the data, enabling users to interact with visualizations, filter data, and gain actionable insights in real time. Ultimately, this project aims to contribute to the growing field of data-driven decision-making within the short-term rental market, fostering a deeper understanding of the dynamics that influence the Airbnb platform. The goal of

this project is to provide a comprehensive analysis of Airbnb listings, focusing on key aspects such as location, pricing, availability, and guest reviews. By utilizing real-world datasets, this study explores patterns, trends, and insights that can assist hosts, potential investors, and stakeholders in making data-driven decisions.

9. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION :

The key problem lies in the absence of a user-friendly, interactive platform that allows for comprehensive analysis and visualization of Airbnb data, enabling users to uncover hidden trends, make informed decisions, and optimize their strategies based on real-time insights. This project seeks to address these issues by providing an intuitive and interactive web application that makes complex data more accessible, actionable, and engaging. For stakeholders such as investors, city planners, and tourism professionals, there is a lack of centralized, actionable insights from Airbnb's data that could drive strategic decisions. Existing tools for analyzing Airbnb data are often limited in scope, static in nature, or difficult for non-technical users to interact with.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

Once the data was collected, it underwent thorough cleaning and preprocessing to ensure its quality and consistency. This involved:

- Handling missing data: Imputing or removing rows with missing values.
- Removing duplicates: Identifying and eliminating duplicate entries to maintain data integrity.
- Data transformation: Converting categorical variables (e.g., neighborhood, property type) into numerical formats suitable for analysis.

The final step involved integrating the analysis into an interactive web application using Streamlit. This included:

- Designing interactive dashboards that allow users to filter data, explore trends, and generate visualizations on demand.

- Providing features such as dynamic charts, maps, and sliders for users to interact with the dataset and gain real-time insights.
- Deploying the Streamlit application to a cloud platform (such as Heroku or Streamlit Cloud) for accessibility by stakeholders and users.

Fig(1) : Room Type Distribution

4. METHOD OF COMPARISON :

To assess host performance, key metrics like ratings, reviews, and pricing were compared:

4.1 Host rating comparison: Average ratings were compared across listings in different cities, examining whether higher-rated listings are more prevalent in certain regions or types of properties.

4.2 Review count vs. rating comparison: A comparative analysis of the number of reviews against ratings was done to understand if listings with more reviews tend to have higher or lower ratings and how this varies across different markets.

This analysis compared how different property types (e.g., entire homes, private rooms, shared spaces) and amenities (e.g., Wi-Fi, air conditioning, parking) influence pricing, demand, and guest satisfaction:

4.3 Price comparison by property type: The average price for different property types was compared to assess whether entire homes, apartments, or rooms had significant pricing differences.

4.4 Amenities comparison: Listings with specific amenities (e.g., pools, hot tubs) were compared to those without to analyze how amenities impact both pricing and booking rates.

Fig(2) : Short Term Rentals

5. CONCLUSION :

Overall, this study contributes to the growing body of knowledge in the short-term rental market by providing a clear, actionable overview of Airbnb trends, offering practical recommendations for hosts to enhance their listings, optimize pricing, and improve guest satisfaction. The interactive Streamlit application developed as part of this project offers an intuitive tool for users to explore these insights in real-time, making the analysis both accessible and actionable. By allowing users to filter, visualize, and analyze Airbnb data dynamically, this

platform enables data-driven decision-making for hosts, travelers, and industry professionals. The project also underscores the power of interactive data visualization tools like Streamlit in democratizing data insights and fostering informed decision-making in the fast-evolving Airbnb ecosystem.

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